

Abstract

Comparative Analysis of Bacterial Lipopolysaccharide Detection on Surfaces of Concanavalin A Using DNA Aptamers and QCM-D Method [†]

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Abstract: Bacterial lipopolysaccharides (LPSs) are important indicators of a bacteria presence in any samples. They can therefore be used for the detection of microbiological contamination in food and dairy products. We performed a comparative analysis of different bacterial models by the application of liposomes containing LPS from *Salmonella enterica* serotype typhimurium on the surface of an 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) monolayer chemisorbed on the gold surface of quartz crystal. Using quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D), we were able to monitor the formation of the lectin, concanavalin A (ConA), layer on the MUA surface. We determined the optimal concentration of the ConA for the layer formation. ConA of 0.3 mg/mL was selected as the most suitable adsorption of liposomes containing LPS. Using the Sauerbrey equation, we calculated that approximately 1.13×10^{12} ConA molecules per cm^2 was adsorbed on the MUA surface, which closely corresponds to the 1.19×10^{12} molecules per cm^2 by theoretical models. Later, mixed LPS liposomes containing dipalmitoyl phosphatidyl choline (DPPC), dipalmitoyl phosphatidyl ethanolamine (DPPE) and cholesterol successfully interacted with the ConA layer, which resulted in a decrease in the resonant frequency and an increase in dissipation. We compared the adsorption of liposomes with different fractions of LPS and containing LPS from different bacteria. Lack of any LPS in liposomes caused weaker adsorption on the ConA layer. Liposomes containing 50% LPS caused the most prominent adsorption and were suitable for interaction with DNA aptamers specific to certain LPS. The addition of the aptamers to the surface of ConA covered by LPS-containing liposomes resulted in a decrease in resonant frequency and an increase in the dissipation. Using the Kelvin–Voigt viscoelastic model and multiharmonic response of acoustic sensors, we also determined changes in viscoelastic values of the molecular films during interaction with liposomes and the ConA layer.

Keywords: lipopolysaccharides; biosensor; DNA aptamers; liposomes; QCM-D

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